

Cascaded FPGA-based FIR filter for ultrasound imaging applications using the DSP Builder Tool

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Abstract—In this paper, we present the design and implementation of an FPGA-based cascaded digital low-pass FIR filter (DLPF) for raw ultrasound echo signals. The proposed filter design takes advantage of the symmetry proprieties of the conventional FIR filter for reducing the number of multipliers by half. The DLPF was built as a tapped cascaded interconnection of identical FIR subfilters within the Matlab/Simulink environment combined with the DSP Builder toolbox, allowing complete model simulation and automatic hardware description language code generation. In order to evaluate our design, we employed symmetrical 4-tap cascaded FIR filter structures to implement a 16-, 24- and 32-tap DLPF filter, respectively. Assuming a pass band frequency of 3.2 MHz and a stop band frequency of 8 MHz, the accuracy and performance of the DLPF are analyzed for different filter orders, coefficient length and two filter design methods: Equiripple and Least-Squares. The normalized root mean square error (NRMSE) cost function is used for comparison with the reference double-precision floating-point values obtained by FDATool in Matlab. The implementation results demonstrate excellent performance and agreement between the Matlab reference design and the hardware experiments using the FPGA-based system. This methodology can be used as an alternative to accelerate the investigation of new DSP algorithms based on hardware for ultrasound imaging.

Keywords— Ultrasound, Filtering, Imaging Process, FPGA.

I. INTRODUCTION

Digital filters are among the most significant components to improve the image quality in medical ultrasound imaging. They are used to separate the echo radiofrequency (RF) information from the undesirable speckle noise generated from the non-homogenous structure of the tissue [1]. Typically, FIR filters are often preferred to IIR filters because of their suitable properties, such as inherent stability, linear phase characteristic and easiness for implementation [2][3].

In order to reduce the complexity and the processing latency in the filter design, several hardware-based algorithms implemented in Very Large Scale Integrated (VLSI) circuits and Field-Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGA), have been proposed by the scientific community [4-6]. In common, all these studies reported significant hardware requirements, which can be a problem in terms of power consumption, latency and chip area occupation. In this paper, we present the design, implementation and evaluation of an efficient FPGA-based digital low-pass FIR filter (DLPF) for ultrasound imaging applications using the Intel DSP Builder toolbox in the Matlab/Simulink environment, allowing complete model simulation and automatic hardware description language (HDL) code generation.

II. METHOD

Each value of the output sequence of a conventional discrete time FIR filter of order N can be expressed as a weighted sum of the most recent input values by the following discrete convolution sum form:

$$y(n) = a_0x(n) + a_1x(n+1) + \dots + a_Nx(n-N) = \sum_{i=0}^N a_i x(n-i) \quad (1)$$

where n is the sample index ($n = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N$), $x(n)$ is the input signal, $y(n)$ is the output signal and a_i is the coefficient of the filter. By taking advantage of the symmetry impulse response (i.e., $a_0 = a_N, a_1 = a_{N-1}, \dots$) and assuming an odd N -order ($N+1$ taps), the computational cost and FPGA resource requirements can be reduced by about half to produce an efficient hardware realization. The corresponding FIR filter architecture is presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Proposed DLPF architecture to produce an efficient hardware realization.

In this study, two filter design methods were applied to evaluate the tradeoff between the number of bits (b) in the coefficient length and filter order (N) via Equiripple and Least-Squares methods. The hardware design was modeled using the DSP Builder development tool, which allows the automatic generation of high-level hardware description language code for Intel FPGAs directly from the Matlab/Simulink environment. The generated VHDL (Very High Speed Integrated Circuits HDL) code was synthesized for and Intel EP4SGX230 Stratix IV FPGA and validated on a Tercasic DE4-320 board.

In order to evaluate our design, we employed symmetrical two, three and four cascaded FIR filter structures to implement a 16-, 24- and 32-tap DLPF filter, respectively. The proposed strategy using Matlab scripts and Simulink models provides flexibility to evaluate different filter orders with adjustable coefficient length. The filter coefficient values were calculated by using the Matlab FDATool and exported to the Matlab workspace. The complete specification of the proposed filter design is presented in Table I.

TABLE I. PROPOSED DIGITAL LOW-PASS FILTER SPECIFICATIONS.

Parameter	Specification
Filter Order (N)	16, 24 and 32
Sampling Rate (F_s)	40 MHz
Pass Band (F_{pass})	3.2 MHz
Stop Band (F_{stop})	8 MHz
Pass Band Ripple (A_{pass})	1 dB
Stop Band Ripple (A_{stop})	50 dB
Filter Design Method	Equiripple and Least-Squares

As illustrated in Fig. 2 for $N=32$, the top-level design architecture consists of the following components: tapped cascade FIR subfilters, a parallel adder to combine the partial sums output from the subfilters. Fig. 3 shows the subfilter subsystem implemented to modularize and simplify the design with $b=17$. Initially, the input “RF_signal” block casts double precision raw RF data loaded from the Matlab workspace into 16-bit signed fixed-point representation for hardware efficiency. Based on equation (1), the convolution sum is obtained by the interconnection of identical tapped FIR subfilters. These blocks consist of four shared “Multiplier” blocks based on predefined signed fractional coefficients, four “Parallel Adder” used to reduce the number of multipliers to $N/2$, and eight “Delay” blocks. Each block has two input signals and three output signals. Signals “In_From_1” and “Out_Goto_1” are the input of the incoming samples and the output signal delayed by an amount of 4 cycles, respectively. To simplify the design, each subfilter has a “Parallel Adder” block to sum the multipliers result, which is available from the

Fig. 2. Top-level of the DLPF using the DSP Builder Blockset.

Fig. 3. Subfilter Implementation (Subsystem1 in Fig. 2)

“Out1” signal. The signals “In_From_2” and “Out_Goto_2” have the same function of the previous signals, however, used for the incoming samples of the second half of the filter. Finally, a Parallel Adder” block with four inputs is used to sum the convolution result of each subfilter.

The experiments were conducted using three different input test signals: (i) a sinusoidal signal of 1 MHz (80% of total amplitude contribution) added to a higher frequency of 8 MHz (20% of total amplitude contribution) sinusoidal signal; (ii) a linear chirp signal from 1 MHz to 10 MHz; and (iii) real ultrasound phantom data acquired from an ultrasound platform developed by our research group [7]. In the last case, the echo data were digitized from the central element (64th) of a 128-element convex transducer (3.2 MHz, AT3C52B – BroadSound Corp.) and a tissue-mimicking phantom (Model 84-317, Fluke Corp.). In all the experiments, a series of 2000 data samples with 12-bit resolution sampled at 40 MSPS was used.

The performance of the proposed scheme was examined by the normalized root mean square error (NRMSE) cost function (2), where n is the sample index, M is the number of samples, h_y is the reference filter information with double-precision floating point obtained by FDATool in Matlab/Simulink as a gold standard, and \bar{h}_y is the information obtained by the implemented algorithm. The NRMSE signifies the relative difference between the reference results and the measured data, with NRMSE <10%, 10-20%, 20-30%, and >30% showing excellent, good, fair, and poor model performance, respectively [8][9].

$$NRMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{n=0}^{M-1} |y(n) - h_y(n)|^2}{\sum_{n=0}^{M-1} |h_y - \bar{h}_y|^2}} * 100 \quad (2)$$

III. RESULTS

To qualitatively illustrate the accuracy of the proposed FPGA-based DLPF, Fig. 4(a) and (b) show the filter impulse response using the Equiripple and Least-Squares filter desing methods, respectively, compared with the reference Matlab FDATool design for $N=32$ and $b=17$.

Fig. 4. Qualitative comparison between the reference Matlab FDATool and the proposed DLPF impulse responses for $N=32$ and $b=17$ using (a) the Equiripple and (b) Least-Squares filter desing methods.

Considering the impulse response evaluation, the calculated NRMSE for the Equiripple and Least-Squares filter design methods were 0.33% and 0.36%, respectively, all showing excellent agreement with the reference data. After been verified and validated on Simulink using the DSP Builder blocks, the generated VHDL output files were synthesized and compiled with the Quartus II 15.1 (Intel Corp., USA) software. To qualitatively illustrate the accuracy of the proposed approach, Figs. 5, 6 and 7 show the graphical comparison between the input and the experimental output signal of the proposed DLPF design for $N=32$ and $b=17$.

Fig. 5(a) shows the reference 1 MHz sinusoidal input signal added to the 8 MHz sinusoidal noise signal, which can easily be seen in its spectrum in Fig. 5(b). On the other hand, Fig. 5(c) presents the processed signal by the DLPF computation. As it can be seen in its spectrum, in Fig. 5(d), the 8 MHz component was completely eliminated. Fig. 6(a) and (b) show the reference chirp input signal from 1MHz to 10 MHz and its spectrum, respectively. As shown in Fig 6(d), the 8 MHz component was reduced to less than 50 dB. Fig. 7(a) and (b) show the real echo data input signal added to the 8 MHz sinusoidal noise signal and its spectrum, respectively. As shown in Fig 7(c), the noise signal was dramatically reduced, confirmed by its FFT analysis, shown in Fig. 7(d).

Fig. 5. Graphical comparison between the input signal and the experimental output signal. (a) Reference 1 MHz signal added to the 8 MHz signal and (b) its spectrum. (c) Experimental output filter response and (d) its spectrum.

Fig. 6. Graphical comparison between the input signal and the experimental output signal. (a) Reference 1-10 MHz chirp signal and (b) its spectrum. (c) Experimental output filter response and (d) its spectrum.

Fig. 7. Graphical comparison between the input signal and the experimental output signal. (a) Reference real echo signal added to the 8 MHz signal and (b) its spectrum. (c) Experimental output filter response and (d) its spectrum.

To qualitatively illustrate the accuracy of the proposed approach, Fig. 8 and Fig. 9 present a quantitative analysis to verify the optimum value of b (8 to 17) and N (16, 24 and 32), for the Equiripple and Least-Squares filter design methods, respectively. As it can be seen, both results converge from $N=32$ and $b=12$.

Table II presents the Intel EP4SGX230 FPGA utilization summary for the proposed architecture that uses less than 1% of the hardware resources, including Adaptive Look-Up Table - ALUT, Adaptive Logic Module - ALM and DSP 18-bit elements for some evaluated designs.

Fig. 8. Normalized root mean square error for $N=16, 24$ and 32 , and $b=8$ to 17 for the Equiripple filter design method.

Fig. 9. Normalized root mean square error for $N=16, 24$ and 32 , and $b=8$ to 17 for the Least-Square filter design method.

TABLE II. FPGA UTILIZATION SUMMARY

FPGA Resources	N=16 b=17	N=24 b=17	N=32 b=17	Total (100%)
ALUTs	260	368	520	182,400
ALM	0	0	0	91,200
DSP 18 bit	16	24	32	1,288

IV. CONCLUSION

We present an efficient, simple and cost-effective hardware-based digital cascaded low-pass filter for real-time ultrasound imaging using DSP Builder blocks in Matlab/Simulink. The implementation results for two design methods, with different number of bits in the coefficient length and filter order, demonstrate excellent performance and agreement between the Matlab reference design and the hardware experiments using the FPGA-based system. The presented results demonstrate the potential of our approach for real-time biomedical ultrasound imaging, including multichannel noise reduction and filtering. This methodology can be used as an alternative to accelerate the investigation of new DSP algorithms based on hardware.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to thank UTFPR, CAPES, CNPq, Fundação Araucária, FINEP and the Brazilian Ministry of Health for the financial support.

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